

The Evolution of Inclusive Education in Cameroon: Implementation Challenges and Success Strategies

Mbeng, Simon Nsah (Ph.D)

Service of Inclusive Education,
Ministry of Basic Education in Cameroon
mbeng1969@gmail.com

Abstract

One of the main issues in today's global debates over education is inclusive education, and Cameroon's progress in this area is significant to educators because it has the potential to improve the psychosocial welfare of people with disabilities. This is demonstrated by Cameroon's dedication to the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), especially SDG 4, which demonstrates the resolve of decision-makers to guarantee inclusive, equitable, and high-quality education for all of her citizens in a setting that is safe, healthy, and protective to eliminate all forms of educational inequality. Its evolution in Cameroon takes into consideration the changes that favour inclusive education across the educational landscape of Cameroon. Also, the challenges of its implementation and psychosocial intervention strategies that foster its implementation have been identified.

Keywords : Development of Inclusive Education; Psycho-social wellness

Introduction

Inclusive education is one of the major concerns in current discussions about education worldwide. The work of individuals, groups, organisations, governments, the United Nations and its affiliated agencies has been at the forefront of this awareness. Their commitment has given the national and worldwide conversation around inclusive education direction and the background information it needs. One of Cameroon's top educational priorities is the creation of inclusive education for psychosocial wellness.

The meaning of inclusive education:

The term "inclusive education" has several definitions. Recently, the UNESCO definition of inclusive education has gained widespread acceptance. This definition states that inclusive education is:

a process of addressing and responding to the diversity of needs of learners through increasing participation in learning, cultures, and communities, and reducing exclusion within and from education. It involves changes in content, approaches, structures, and strategies with a common vision, which covers all children within an appropriate age range. It embodies the conviction that it is the responsibility of the mainstream education system to educate all children. (UNESCO, 2005).

Doncheva, Al-Obaydi and Hussein (2023) state that inclusive education is an educational philosophy which considers all the necessary systematic educational parameters, such as the identification of those with special needs, referrals, diagnosis and finally the development of an individualised education plan. These are accompanied by adaptive content, structures, approaches, strategies, resources and specialised human resources.

Tchombe (2012) states that inclusive education in Cameroon began with an assessment of the policies, practices, and obstacles to inclusive education within the primary education sector in 2012. Tchombe (2012) further believes that policies and the means by which they are implemented are crucial for the successful implementation of inclusive education. Through a series of policy declarations, the Cameroonian government has acted since 1983 to safeguard the right of all children to an education, particularly those who have disabilities. However, these regulations have serious flaws that make it challenging to implement inclusive teaching.

Due to the lack of a systematic situational analysis, some of the imperfections in the implementation process may be related to the policy models (such as top-bottom rather than bottom-top). The law of 13th April 2010 stipulates the provision of special education, psychosocial support, socio-economic integration, medical prevention and access to employment, infrastructure, housing and transport for persons with disabilities, among other issues, but missed out on the concept of inclusive education and its practices. The inclusive education environment in Cameroon has changed significantly in both the public and private education sectors. The goal of this modification is to ensure that individuals with special needs have equitable access to high-quality education (Cockburn et al., 2017).

Cameroonian reforms that support inclusive education

A number of policy initiatives undertaken by the Cameroonian government have favoured the development of inclusive education in the nation. These measures include:

1. Policy framework: To encourage inclusive education, the Cameroonian government has enacted various laws and policies. Among these is Law No. 2010/002 of April 13, 2010, Section 33 (1-4), which provides specifics on how to design buildings and institutions to enhance accessibility and use for people with disabilities. Education is a key component of the 2030 Sustainable Development Agenda, according to the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), which Cameroon signed in 2015. The SDG4 seeks to fulfil the education agenda that hasn't been completed since the MDGs by going above and beyond, with a pledge by:

“All countries to ensure equal access to quality learning opportunities at all levels of education in a lifelong learning perspective.” The SDG4 calls on subscribing states to "ensure access for all to inclusive and equitable quality education" and "promote lifelong learning opportunities."

The Target (4.1) states that:

“by 2030, ensure that all girls and boys complete a full course of free, quality primary and secondary education that leads to a real chance to learn.”

The Target 4.a specifies to:

“build or adapt schools that are suitable for children, people with disabilities and both sexes, and provide an effective learning environment that is safe, free from violence and accessible to all.”

The Target 4.5 advocates:

“eliminating gender inequalities in education by 2030 and ensuring equal access to all levels of education and vocational training for vulnerable people, including people with disabilities, indigenous people and children in vulnerable situations”.

Decree No. 2018/6233/PM of 26 July 2018, spelling out practical details for the implementation of the said law, stipulates in Article 4 that learners with certain disabilities should stay on the ground floor of storey buildings or near the chalkboard, as their disabilities require. The ministries of education and social affairs are developing inclusive education policies for the state of Cameroon. With respect to this common interest, the ministries have developed a National Policy on Inclusive Education for Cameroon.

2. Inclusive curriculum: In order to include inclusive education practices and concepts, the national curriculum has been updated. Providing a wide variety of educational resources for kids with special needs is part of this. This is in conformity with Decree No. 2012/268 of June 11, 2012, which organises the Ministry of Basic Education and creates a Service for Inclusive Education.

3. Training of teachers: Capacities of educators are being reinforced nationwide in inclusive education and special education. This aligns with Ministerial letter No B2/1464/N/MINEDUB/SG/DEMP/SDEP/SEI dated 11th October 2024, which addresses the reinforcement of teachers' capacities in inclusive education. The educational sector ministries have been heavily involved in providing in-service training for teachers. The Ministry of Basic Education is noticeably at the frontline stage in this domain.

4. Infrastructure and accessibility: Measures are being taken to improve on physical accessibility of schools for learners with disabilities. This includes the construction of ramps, accessible toilets, administrative buildings and mobility canes. Similarly, efforts are being taken to ensure that learners with other social vulnerabilities such as children who are internally displaced or refugees learn well in a few chosen schools.

5. Inclusive schools: The government has created inclusive nursery and primary schools in different subdivisions of the country to take care of children with special needs. These serve as pilot schools for inclusive education and offer support and resources for learners with special needs.

6. Inclusive school policies: Some schools have adopted inclusive policies that promote the enrollment and retention of learners with special needs. These policies include offering scholarships, flexible school fees, provision and adaptation of material and equipment to meet the needs of the children.

7. Community engagement: There has been an increase in community engagement and awareness campaigns to promote inclusive education. This has changed societal attitude towards persons with disabilities and promote inclusion in schools and communities. This community advocacy on inclusive education is gradually gaining grounds in the education communities of Cameroon.

8. Working strategies/tools: Education stakeholders are being made aware of the concept of inclusive education, a national policy on inclusive education which was validated in 2024, an identification tool for children with special needs in schools which was validated in 2023, a repository for special educational needs and specialized pedagogic/andragogic resources which have equally been developed and validated based on the types of special needs in 2024, inclusive school environment norms have been validated in 2024, and teachers and supervisors are undergoing in-service training on various teaching strategies for persons with special needs.

9. Creation of inclusive schools : According to Decision NO 7707/A/SEI/MINEDUB/SG/DEMP/ of 4th August 2015 the Ministry of Basic Education initially created 69 inclusive primary schools during the first phase of the pilot program. This led to another Ministerial Decision No 79/A/501/MINEDUB/SG/DEMP/ of 27th September 2023 creating 360 nursery and 360 primary inclusive schools during the on-going second phase of the pilot program. Currently, every subdivision in Cameroon has a nursery and primary inclusive schools. In addition, the private educational sector such as the Cameroon Baptist Convention, is equally doing a lot in putting up inclusive schools.

Although these changes signify noteworthy advancements in Cameroon's inclusive education system, there remains ample room for further improvement. There are still a lot of issues, such as a lack of resources and unfavourable social perceptions among learners with impairments. However, there are encouraging improvements and a bright future for inclusive education in Cameroon because of the government's dedication to it and the efforts of other partners.

Challenges to the implementation of inclusive education in Cameroon

Mbibe (2013) states that the implementation of inclusive education in Cameroon has the following challenges:

1. Lack of infrastructure and resources: Lack of proper infrastructure and resources is a major concern. Many schools are unable to accommodate learners with special needs because of a lack of wheelchair ramps, accessible toilets, or specialised learning materials.
2. Limited teacher training and expertise: The majority of teachers in Cameroon have not received proper training or have limited knowledge about teaching learners with special needs.
3. Negative attitudes and stigma: People with special needs in Cameroon often face discrimination and societal stigma, which can hinder their access to education. This negative attitude towards disabilities and other social vulnerabilities also extends to teachers and other learners. This makes it difficult for learners with special needs to feel comfortable in the classroom.
4. Inadequate funding and government support: Inclusive education requires significant investment and support from the government, but funding for inclusive education and training programmes is often limited in Cameroon. This makes it challenging to provide necessary accommodations and support for all learners.
5. Limited access to educational opportunities: Children with disabilities in Cameroon often live in remote or rural areas with limited access to schools, especially schools that offer inclusive education. This creates significant barriers for these children to receive education. Consequently, they do not enjoy their right to education like all other children.
6. Language barriers: Cameroon has over 240 indigenous languages, and this linguistic diversity makes language acquisition very challenging for children with language impairment, as many schools do not have materials or teachers who can communicate in their native language.
7. Inadequate assessment and evaluation techniques: For pupils with special needs, Cameroon's standardised testing and assessment practices can frequently be a barrier. It is challenging for pupils with special needs to demonstrate their knowledge and skills since these approaches fail to consider their varied learning needs and capacities.
8. Lack of collaboration and coordination among stakeholders: The absence of collaboration and coordination among various stakeholders, including government agencies, schools, teachers, parents, and disability organisations, is a great issue. In Cameroon, there is often a lack of communication and cooperation between these groups, leading to challenges in implementing inclusive education practices.
9. Cultural beliefs and practices: Certain Cameroonian communities hold cultural beliefs and customs that regard disability as a punishment or a curse. This may lead to the exclusion, discrimination, and inability of children with impairments to participate in inclusive education programmes.
10. Limited focus on individual needs: Meeting the unique requirements and learning preferences of pupils with particular needs is the main goal of inclusive education. One major obstacle to inclusive

education for learners with special needs in Cameroon is the country's inclination towards a uniform approach to education.

11) Conflict in the inclusive education process: Divergent viewpoints exist on Cameroon's adoption of an inclusive educational method. Curriculum developers believe that they have the monopoly on defining the pathway to inclusive education, while the policymakers see themselves as the only rightful persons to decide on the implementation pathway. Unfortunately, there are many charlatans who have little or no knowledge of inclusive education but claim to be inclusive education experts.

12) The workability of inclusive education: Many education stakeholders in Cameroon doubt the workability of inclusive education. Many see inclusive education as a myth.

13) There is low appropriation and use of educational technologies in inclusive education and training institutions in Cameroon.

14) Difficulties in curriculum adaptation: Adapting the curriculum in Cameroon is a difficult undertaking. This is due to the fact that the majority of courses were created without taking special needs students into account. Despite its inherent benefits, some perceive inclusive education as a threat to the official school curriculum. This is due to the fact that a teacher would rather cover their programme and stay out of problems with education authorities than adhere to inclusive education and face criticism for not meeting the requirements of the syllabus and curriculum (Cockburn et al., 2017).

Interventions for successful inclusive education:

Cameroon's National Policy on Inclusive Education (2024) has put forward the following intervention strategies for successful inclusive education:

1. Government Support and Inclusive Policies: The government is putting in place policies that promote inclusive education. These include allocating adequate resources and funding, training teachers on management of individuals with special needs, and enforcing anti-discrimination laws.

2. Increased Awareness and Sensitisation: There is increased sensitisation of the public on the importance and benefits of inclusive education. Media campaigns, community outreach programmes, and workshops for parents, teachers, and community leaders accomplish this.

3. Collaboration and Partnership: There is more collaboration and partnership between government agencies, NGOs, and other stakeholders to support inclusive education programs in Cameroon. This helps in sharing resources, expertise, and best practices to address the challenges.

4. Professional Development and Training for Teachers: Teachers are undergoing professional development and training on how to successfully instruct learners with special needs. This includes training on inclusive teaching methods, identifying and addressing learning barriers, and creating an inclusive classroom environment.

5. Specialising Support Services: The government is putting in place progressive mechanisms for the recruitment of specialised teachers in schools to assist learners with special needs. This will help improve their learning outcomes and social integration.

6. Parental Involvement: To provide a supportive and inclusive learning environment for children, parents of children with special needs must be involved in the educational process, and their thoughts and feedback must be appreciated.

7. Addressing Infrastructure and Accessibility: There is a need to improve the physical and psychological accessibility of schools to accommodate all learners with special needs. This includes installing ramps and wheelchair-friendly facilities, as well as providing assistive devices and technology to support learning.

8. Inclusive Curriculum and Materials: The curriculum and learning materials used in schools should be inclusive and reflect the diversity of learners. This can help in promoting cultural diversity and respect for all learners, regardless of their abilities.

9. Monitoring and Evaluation: There should be an effective follow-up and evaluation system to assess the progress and impact of inclusive education programmes. This can help in identifying areas that need improvement and ensure equal access to quality education.

10.) Throughout the implementation phase, consult experts in inclusive education to refine the approach to inclusive education and avoid charlatans.

11.) Provide psycho-social support for children in emergency situations. This can take the form of:

- establishing an education structure where children feel included.
- providing a reliable and interactive living environment through school or another organised educational activity.
- offering activities in groups and teams (sports, theatre, dance, games, etc.) that require cooperation.
- providing opportunities for social integration and unity.
- enhancing children's development by providing varied educational activities.

Conclusion

The Cameroon government and its educational stakeholders have initiated policies aimed at fostering inclusive education despite its implementation challenges. In order to curb these challenges, intervention strategies for successful inclusive education are being put in place. Promoting inclusive, equitable, and high-quality education is a priority for the Cameroonian government and its educational stakeholders. For it to succeed, Cameroon government and her educational stakeholders need to become agents of change bearing in mind that the great aim of education is not knowledge, but action and action now.

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